

Original article

Pattern of Brain Computed Tomographic Findings among Adult Patients with Non-Traumatic Brain Injury at Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Computed tomography (CT) remains the primary imaging modality for acute neurological assessment in resource-limited settings due to its speed, availability, and diagnostic accuracy. Non-traumatic brain injury (nTBI) includes a broad range of vascular, infectious, neoplastic, and degenerative conditions and contributes significantly to neurological morbidity in northern Nigeria. Despite the high volume of CT examinations at Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital (AKTH), there has been no documented reference pattern of findings in this population. The study aimed to describe the pattern of brain CT findings and identify the most common clinical indications among adult patients with nTBI at AKTH, Kano. **Materials and methods:** A prospective cross-sectional study was conducted from November 2020 to June 2021 at the Radiology Department of AKTH. A total of 195 adult patients (17–65 years) with suspected nTBI were consecutively enrolled. Brain CT scans were performed using a 160-slice Aquilion Prime scanner (Toshiba, Japan, 2011). Demographic data, clinical indications, and CT findings were collected and analysed using descriptive statistics and inferential tests (Chi-square and Fisher's Exact Test) with significance set at $p < 0.05$. **Results:** The study population comprised 49.7% males and 50.3% females, with a mean age of 44.87 ± 15.20 years. Stroke was the most common clinical indication (males 18.6%; females 21.4%), with no significant sex difference ($p = 0.616$). Normal CT findings were most frequent overall, while cerebral infarction was the leading abnormality. Grouped analysis showed cerebrovascular conditions as the predominant indication (36.4%), with ischaemic infarcts (23.6%) and haemorrhages (6.2%) as the most common abnormalities. No statistically significant sex differences were observed in clinical indications or CT findings. **Conclusion:** Normal CT scans were the most frequent finding, and cerebral infarction was the most common abnormal finding. The absence of significant sex differences suggests a non-sex-specific pattern of nTBI in this population. These findings provide baseline reference data for clinical decision-making and resource planning in similar settings, with MRI recommended as a complementary modality when necessary.

Keywords: Brain CT findings, Cerebral infarct, Computed tomography, Nigeria; Non-traumatic brain injury, Sex differences, Stroke

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Introduction

The brain is the principal organ of the central nervous system (CNS), lying within the cranial vault and weighing approximately 1,400 g in the adult. ¹ It is conventionally divided into the hindbrain, midbrain, and forebrain, and is responsible for motor, sensory, cognitive, and autonomic functions. ^{1,2} The brain represents 2% of body weight yet consumes 15% of cardiac output, underlining its metabolic vulnerability to any disruption of blood or oxygen supply. ^{2,3,4} Non-traumatic brain injury (nTBI) is defined as a disease of the brain that impairs its structure or function, resulting in deficits in cognition, communication,

physical function, and/or psychosocial behaviour.^{5,6,7} Brain injuries of non-traumatic origin can produce negative and long-term consequences on a patient's quality of life.^{6,7}

Stroke is the leading cause of neurological morbidity and mortality in sub-Saharan Africa and constitutes a growing public health burden in Nigeria.^{8,9,10} A systematic review and meta-analysis by Adeloye et al.¹¹ estimated the pooled stroke prevalence in Nigeria at 1.53 per 1,000 population, with haemorrhagic subtypes carrying disproportionately higher mortality than ischaemic stroke. The Global Burden of Disease Study 2016 further established neurological disorders as one of the leading causes of disability-adjusted life years worldwide, with stroke and other cerebrovascular conditions accounting for the greatest share of this burden.⁸ Beyond stroke, the spectrum of nTBI includes infectious conditions (meningitis, encephalitis, cerebral abscess), autoimmune disorders (vasculitis, multiple sclerosis), intracranial neoplasms, and neurodegenerative diseases such as Parkinson's disease and dementia.^{11,12}

Among available neuroimaging modalities, CT offers practical advantages in resource-limited settings: it is rapid, widely accessible, and highly sensitive for detecting intracranial haemorrhage and mass lesions. Compared with magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), CT is less time-consuming, more available in tertiary hospitals across northern Nigeria, and can be performed safely in patients with implantable cardiac devices.¹³ Joint imaging guidelines from the American Society of Neuroradiology, American College of Radiology, and the Society of NeuroInterventional Surgery recommend CT as the first-line imaging investigation for patients presenting with acute stroke and transient ischaemic attack.¹⁴ Although associated with ionising radiation, its diagnostic utility in the acute neurological setting remains indispensable.¹⁵

In standard radiological practice, each imaging facility is expected to maintain documented reference data for common examinations. However, prior to this study, no such data on brain CT findings among adult patients with nTBI were available at Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital (AKTH). A previous study at AKTH by Dambatta and Sidi¹⁶ was limited to paediatric traumatic head injury, leaving a gap in the literature for the adult non-traumatic population. This study aimed to evaluate the pattern of brain CT findings among adult patients with nTBI at Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital, Nigeria.

Materials and methods

This was a prospective cross-sectional study conducted among adult patients with non-traumatic brain injury (nTBI) at Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital (AKTH) in Kano, Nigeria, from November 2020 to June 2021. Ethical clearance to conduct the study was obtained from the Human Research and Ethics Committee of AKTH (Approval No.: NHREC/28/01/2020/AKTH/EC/2917; Approval Date: 2nd November 2020), in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Informed consent was obtained from each patient. A consecutive sampling technique was employed, enrolling all eligible patients during the study period, and included 195 patients (97 males and 98 females). Adult patients aged 17 to 65 years presenting with any nTBI were included in the study. Exclusion criteria included patients with a history of traumatic head injury, patients for CT examinations of other body regions, and paediatric (<17 years) or geriatric (>65 years) patients. A 160-slice Aquilion Prime CT scanner (Toshiba, Japan, 2011) and a structured data capture sheet were used to collect data. Age, sex, clinical history, and CT indication were retrieved from patient request forms and recorded into the structured data capture sheet. The height and weight were measured and recorded. The Body mass index (BMI) was calculated as weight (kg) divided by height squared (m²), and body surface area (BSA) was estimated using the Mosteller formula. BMI and BSA were recorded as descriptive baseline parameters to characterise the study population; they were not incorporated into inferential analysis but are retained for future studies investigating associations between metabolic risk factors and CT findings. CT findings were obtained from the written reports of consultant radiologists and transcribed into the data capture. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were applied for the data analysis. Means, standard deviations, ranges, frequencies, and percentages were obtained using descriptive statistics. The chi-square (χ^2) test and Fisher's Exact tests were performed to assess the observed differences in clinical indications and CT findings between males and females. The data were analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (IBM SPSS) Version 22.0, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

A total of 195 patients were enrolled, comprising 97 (49.7%) males and 98 (50.3%) females, with a male-to-female ratio of approximately 1:1. The mean age

was 44.87±15.20 years (range: 17–65). Mean BMI was 23.98±3.50 kg/m² and mean BSA was 1.76±0.16 m². Males had a higher mean BSA (1.93±0.20 m²) compared to females (1.58±0.12 m²), reflecting expected anthropometric differences (Table 1).

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of study participants

Variable	Male (n=97)	Female (n=98)	Total (n=195)
Age (years), Mean±SD	45.48±14.78 (17–65)	44.26±15.62 (17–65)	44.87±15.20 (17–65)
BMI (kg/m ²), Mean±SD	24.05±2.94 (16.14–33.04)	23.90±4.05 (13.89–40.82)	23.98±3.50 (13.89–40.82)
BSA (m ²), Mean±SD	1.93±0.20 (1.52–2.61)	1.58±0.12 (1.24–1.93)	1.76±0.16 (1.24–2.61)

BMI: Body Mass Index; BSA: Body Surface Area; SD: Standard Deviation.

Table 2. Frequency distribution of clinical indications by sex (indications with combined frequency ≥3 shown individually)

Clinical Indication	Male n (%)	Female n (%)	Total n (%)
Stroke	18 (18.6)	21 (21.4)	39 (20.0)
Headache	14 (14.4)	16 (16.3)	30 (15.4)
Cerebrovascular disease	11 (11.3)	5 (5.1)	16 (8.2)
Intracranial space-occupying lesion	3 (3.1)	8 (8.2)	11 (5.6)
Weakness	4 (4.1)	3 (3.1)	7 (3.6)
Cerebrovascular accident	3 (3.1)	5 (5.1)	8 (4.1)
Subarachnoid haemorrhage	2 (2.1)	3 (3.1)	5 (2.6)
Optic atrophy	3 (3.1)	1 (1.0)	4 (2.1)
Brain tumour	2 (2.1)	2 (2.0)	4 (2.1)
Subdural haematoma	1 (1.0)	2 (2.0)	3 (1.5)
Transient ischaemic attack	2 (2.1)	1 (1.0)	3 (1.5)
Proptosis	1 (1.0)	2 (2.0)	3 (1.5)
Other indications (each <1%)*	33 (34.0)	29 (29.6)	62 (31.8)
Total	97 (100)	98 (100)	195 (100)

*Other indications include: convulsion, dementia, dysphagia, ischaemia, irrational talk, loss of consciousness, loss of vision, optic disc oedema, rhabdomyosarcoma, ischaemic stroke (as separate entry), thyroid eye disease, vertigo, and others, each occurring once.

A total of 48 distinct clinical indications were documented. Stroke was the most frequent indication (20.0%), followed by headache (15.4%) and cerebrovascular disease (8.2%). Intracranial space-occupying lesions accounted for 5.6% and cerebrovascular accidents for 4.1%. Proptosis, subdural haematoma, and transient ischaemic attack each had the least frequency (1.5% each). No statistically significant sex difference was found for any indication (Table 2). Given the large number of overlapping and clinically related indication labels, these 48 indications were additionally reclassified into six pathophysiologically coherent groups and are presented alongside the detailed list in Table 2a. The 48 documented indications were reclassified into six pathophysiologically coherent groups (Table 2a). Cerebrovascular events constituted the

single largest grouped category (36.4%; n=71), consolidating stroke, cerebrovascular disease, cerebrovascular accident, subarachnoid haemorrhage, and transient ischaemic attack into a unified burden. General neurological presentations accounted for 35.4% (n=69), while headache syndromes comprised 15.4% (n=30). No statistically significant sex difference was identified in any of the grouped categories.

A total of 46 distinct CT diagnoses were recorded. Normal brain study was the most common finding (27.2%), followed by cerebral infarct (16.9%) and brain/cerebral atrophy (16.4%). Given the large number of individual diagnoses, findings were additionally aggregated into eight pathologically coherent groups and are presented in Table 3a. Intracerebral haematoma was descriptively more prevalent in females (6.1% vs. 1.0%), while ischaemic infarct was more frequent in males (4.1% vs. 1.0%). Subdural haematoma occurred exclusively in males (3.1%). The full distribution of CT findings by sex is shown in Table 3. It is noted that subarachnoid haemorrhage was documented as a clinical indication in five patients (Table 2); however, this did not appear as a distinct CT-confirmed diagnosis in radiologist reports. This likely reflects cases in which clinical suspicion of SAH was not radiologically confirmed on non-contrast CT, or in which the CT report captured the underlying cause (e.g., cerebrovascular disease) rather than the SAH itself. This discrepancy is acknowledged as a limitation of retrospective CT report extraction.

The distinct CT diagnosis findings were aggregated into eight clinically coherent groups (Table 3a). When consolidated, ischaemic infarcts collectively represented the most prevalent abnormal category (23.6%; n=46), encompassing cerebral, ischaemic, basal ganglia, pontine, and brain infarcts documented in Table 3. All intracranial haemorrhages combined accounted for 6.2% (n=12). Brain/cerebral atrophy remained the second most frequent grouped abnormality (16.4%; n=32). No

statistically significant sex difference was identified in any of the grouped CT finding categories. Abnormal CT findings were recorded in 75.3% of males and 70.4% of females, while normal brain studies constituted 24.7% and 29.6%, respectively, giving a combined normal rate of 27.2%. The sex difference in proportions of abnormal findings was not statistically significant ($\chi^2=0.579$, $df=1$, $p=0.447$), as summarised in Table 4.

Table 2a. Grouped clinical indications by pathophysiological category and sex

Indication Group*	Male n (%)	Female n (%)	Total n (%)	Test	p-value
Cerebrovascular Events	36 (37.1)	35 (35.7)	71 (36.4)	$\chi^2=0.042$	0.838
Headache Syndromes	14 (14.4)	16 (16.3)	30 (15.4)	$\chi^2=0.134$	0.714
Intracranial Mass Lesions	5 (5.2)	10 (10.2)	15 (7.7)	Fisher's	0.175
Ophthalmological/Orbital	4 (4.1)	3 (3.1)	7 (3.6)	Fisher's	>0.999
Haemorrhagic Presentations	1 (1.0)	2 (2.0)	3 (1.5)	Fisher's	>0.999
General Neurological/Other	37 (38.1)	32 (32.7)	69 (35.4)	$\chi^2=0.643$	0.423
Total	97 (100)	98 (100)	195 (100)		

CVE: stroke, cerebrovascular disease, CVA, SAH, TIA. Headache: headache. Mass lesions: ICSOL, brain tumour. Ophthalmological: proptosis, optic atrophy. Haemorrhagic: subdural haematoma. General/other: weakness and remaining indications (<1% each). CVE: cerebrovascular events; CVA: cerebrovascular accident; SAH: subarachnoid haemorrhage; TIA: transient ischaemic attack; ICSOL: intracranial space-occupying lesion. χ^2 : Pearson chi-square; Fisher's: Fisher's Exact Test. Analyses exploratory.

Table 3. Frequency distribution of brain CT findings by sex

CT Finding	Male n (%)	Female n (%)	Total n (%)
Normal brain study	24 (24.7)	29 (29.6)	53 (27.2)
Cerebral infarct	16 (16.5)	17 (17.3)	33 (16.9)
Brain/cerebral atrophy	15 (15.5)	17 (17.3)	32 (16.4)
Ischaemic infarct	4 (4.1)	1 (1.0)	5 (2.6)
Intracerebral haematoma	1 (1.0)	6 (6.1)	7 (3.6)
Subdural haematoma	3 (3.1)	0 (0.0)	3 (1.5)
Basal ganglia infarct	3 (3.1)	0 (0.0)	3 (1.5)
Cerebral abscess	1 (1.0)	2 (2.0)	3 (1.5)
Pontine infarct	1 (1.0)	2 (2.0)	3 (1.5)
Basal ganglia acute bleed with IVE	2 (2.1)	0 (0.0)	2 (1.0)
Brain tumour	2 (2.1)	0 (0.0)	2 (1.0)
Proptosis	0 (0.0)	2 (2.0)	2 (1.0)
Brain infarct	0 (0.0)	2 (2.0)	2 (1.0)
Other findings (each occurring once per sex) *	25 (25.8)	19 (19.4)	44 (22.6)
Total	97 (100)	98 (100)	195 (100)

IVE: Intraventricular Extension. *Other findings include each diagnosis recorded only once in either sex, including: aggressive maxillary tumour, arachnoid cyst, atherosclerosis of common carotid artery, basal ganglia calcification, basal ganglia haemorrhage, cerebellopontine angle tumour, encephalomalacia, frontal lobe contusion, frontal lobe infarct, glioblastoma multiforme, Grave's ophthalmopathy, hemispheric bleeding, haemorrhagic infarct, intracranial mass, intraventricular haemorrhage, left chronic parietal infarct, meningioma, meningitis, multifocal acute intracranial haemorrhage, maxillary sinusitis, nasal tumour with frontal lobe extension, orbital tumour, parietal lobe ischaemic infarct, pituitary mass adenoma, squamous cell carcinoma, sella mass, sphenoidal and ethmoidal tumour, subacute haematoma, and others.

Table 3a. Grouped brain CT findings by pathological category and sex

CT Finding Group*	Male n (%)	Female n (%)	Total n (%)	Test	p-value
Normal Brain Study	24 (24.7)	29 (29.6)	53 (27.2)	$\chi^2=0.579$	0.447
All Ischaemic Infarcts	24 (24.7)	22 (22.4)	46 (23.6)	$\chi^2=0.142$	0.706
Brain/Cerebral Atrophy	15 (15.5)	17 (17.3)	32 (16.4)	$\chi^2=0.126$	0.723
All Intracranial Haemorrhages	6 (6.2)	6 (6.1)	12 (6.2)	$\chi^2=0.000$	0.985
Tumours/Neoplastic	2 (2.1)	0 (0.0)	2 (1.0)	Fisher's	0.499
Infections	1 (1.0)	2 (2.0)	3 (1.5)	Fisher's	>0.999
Ophthalmological	0 (0.0)	2 (2.0)	2 (1.0)	Fisher's	0.499
Other/Miscellaneous	25 (25.8)	20 (20.4)	45 (23.1)	$\chi^2=0.874$	0.350
Total	97 (100)	98 (100)	195 (100)		

Ischaemic infarcts: cerebral, ischaemic, basal ganglia, pontine, brain infarcts. Atrophy: brain/cerebral atrophy. Haemorrhages: intracerebral haematoma, subdural haematoma, basal ganglia bleed with IVE. Tumours: brain tumour. Infections: cerebral abscess. Ophthalmological: proptosis. Other: 45 remaining single-occurrence diagnoses (see Table 3). IVE: intraventricular extension. χ^2 : Pearson chi-square; Fisher's: Fisher's Exact Test. Analyses exploratory.

Table 4. Overall distribution of normal and abnormal CT findings by sex

Finding Category	Male n (%)	Female n (%)	Total n (%)
Normal	24 (24.7)	29 (29.6)	53 (27.2)
Abnormal	73 (75.3)	69 (70.4)	142 (72.8)
Total	97 (100)	98 (100)	195 (100)

Chi-square (χ^2) and Fisher's Exact tests revealed no statistically significant sex differences in any clinical indication or CT finding, whether examined as individual categories or as pathophysiologically grouped aggregates. For individual findings: Stroke ($\chi^2=0.251$, $p=0.616$), cerebral infarct ($\chi^2=0.025$,

$p=0.874$), intracerebral haematoma (OR=0.16, $p=0.118$), ischaemic infarct (OR=4.17, $p=0.212$), and subdural haematoma (OR= ∞ , $p=0.121$) all showed non-significant differences. For grouped categories: cerebrovascular events combined ($\chi^2=0.042$, $p=0.838$), all ischaemic infarcts ($\chi^2=0.142$, $p=0.706$), and all haemorrhages ($\chi^2=0.000$, $p=0.985$) were similarly non-significant. These exploratory analyses were not adjusted for multiple comparisons and should be interpreted with corresponding caution. The complete inferential results, including grouped analyses, are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Inferential statistics for sex differences in key clinical indications and CT findings

Variable	Test	Statistic	p-value	Significance
Normal vs Abnormal CT (overall)	χ^2	0.579	0.447	Not significant
Stroke indication	χ^2	0.251	0.616	Not significant
Headache indication	χ^2	0.134	0.714	Not significant
Cerebral infarct	χ^2	0.025	0.874	Not significant
Brain/cerebral atrophy	χ^2	0.126	0.723	Not significant
Ischaemic infarct	Fisher's	OR=4.17	0.212	Not significant
Intracerebral haematoma	Fisher's	OR=0.16	0.118	Not significant
Subdural haematoma	Fisher's	OR= ∞	0.121	Not significant
GROUPED ANALYSES				
Cerebrovascular events (combined)	χ^2	0.042	0.838	Not significant
All ischaemic infarcts (combined)	χ^2	0.142	0.706	Not significant
All haemorrhages (combined)	χ^2	0.000	0.985	Not significant
Intracranial mass lesions (combined)	Fisher's	OR=0.48	0.175	Not significant
General neurological/other (combined)	χ^2	0.643	0.423	Not significant

χ^2 : Pearson chi-square test ($df=1$ for all); Fisher's: Fisher's Exact Test used where expected cell count <5 ; OR: Odds Ratio (male vs. female). Grouped rows consolidate clinically related subtypes; constituent entries are listed in Tables 2 and 3 and detailed in Tables 2a and 3a. χ^2 : Pearson chi-square ($df=1$); Fisher's: Fisher's Exact Test (expected cell count <5); OR: Odds Ratio (male vs. female, reference). All analyses are exploratory; no correction for multiple comparisons is applied. $p<0.05$ considered statistically significant; all comparisons two-tailed.

Discussion

The study aimed to describe the pattern of brain CT findings and determine the most common clinical indications among adult patients presenting with non-traumatic brain injury at Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital (AKTH), Kano, as the tertiary hospital receiving the highest number of referrals in the Northeast region.

The findings of this study, as shown in Table 1, were similar to those of the study by Lim and Wong,¹⁸ who reported a near-equal sex distribution in their Hong Kong cohort. The similarities may be attributable to comparable referral practices and the universal disease burden of non-traumatic neurological conditions across both settings, where

neither sex is disproportionately predisposed to seeking CT-indicated neurological care. It should be noted, however, that Lim and Wong studied an emergency department population with a different case mix, selection criteria, and imaging protocol from the present study, which limits the directness of this comparison. However, it was contrary to the findings of studies conducted by Ugwuanyi et al.¹⁷ and Ijeh-Tarila et al.,¹⁹ possibly reflecting differences in referral patterns or disease spectrum across study sites.

At the individual indication level, stroke was the most frequent single referral label in both sexes, consistent with the high burden of cerebrovascular disease in northern Nigeria^{8,11,12} and the growing global neurological disease burden documented by Feigin et al.⁸ When the 48 distinct indications were reclassified into six pathophysiologically groups (Table 2a), cerebrovascular events collectively constituted the largest category (36.4%; $n=71$) – encompassing stroke, cerebrovascular disease, cerebrovascular accident, subarachnoid haemorrhage, and transient ischaemic attack –

more accurately reflecting the full vascular referral burden than any single label alone. Neither the individual stroke indication ($\chi^2=0.251$, $p=0.616$) nor headache ($\chi^2=0.134$, $p=0.714$) nor any grouped indication category showed a statistically significant sex difference. This suggests that the clinical profile of non-traumatic neurological presentations at AKTH is broadly similar between males and females, and that observed percentage differences are attributable to sampling variation rather than true population-level sex disparities. This differs from emergency department-based studies in Italy¹⁵ and Hong Kong,¹⁸ where acute headache and neurological disorders were the predominant referral indications – a discrepancy attributable to differences in patient triage, healthcare access, and disease epidemiology between settings.

Normal brain CT study – defined in this study as a radiologist's report explicitly documenting no acute intracranial abnormality. Mild age-related cerebral atrophy and/or chronic small vessel ischemic changes may be present and are considered physiological for the patient's age rather than pathological. It was the most frequently recorded single finding (27.2% overall), consistent with reports from Ugwuanyi et al.¹⁷ (39%), Zarmehri et al.²² (73%), and Lim and Wong¹⁸ (40.4%). The high proportion of normal scans may reflect the inherently lower sensitivity of CT compared with MRI for early ischaemic changes, small cortical lesions, and posterior fossa pathology, as well as limited pre-CT clinical triage capacity in the study setting. Consistent with joint imaging guidelines recommending CT as first-line for acute neurological presentations,¹⁴ these findings nonetheless highlight the need for structured pre-imaging triage to optimise CT utilisation in resource-limited settings.

At the individual diagnosis level, cerebral infarct was the most prevalent abnormal finding (males 16.5%; females 17.3%), though chi-square testing showed no statistically significant sex difference ($\chi^2=0.025$, $p=0.874$). This aligns with Yunusa et al.²¹ who reported cerebral infarction in 67.1% of stroke patients in Sokoto, north-western Nigeria, supporting the view that cerebral infarction is the dominant non-traumatic brain pathology in this region. At the individual level, brain/cerebral atrophy was the second most common abnormal finding, with no significant sex difference ($\chi^2=0.126$, $p=0.723$). When CT findings were aggregated into clinically coherent groups (Table 3a), all ischaemic infarcts collectively accounted for 23.6% ($n=46$) – the largest abnormal grouped category – while all

intracranial haemorrhages combined comprised 6.2% ($n=12$). These grouped figures more clearly delineate the relative burden of ischaemic versus haemorrhagic disease than the disaggregated list alone. No statistically significant sex difference was found in either the grouped haemorrhagic ($\chi^2=0.000$, $p=0.985$) or grouped ischaemic ($\chi^2=0.142$, $p=0.706$) categories, consistent with the null sex-difference findings across individual entries.

While ischaemic infarct was descriptively more common in males (4.1% vs. 1.0%, OR=4.17) and intracerebral haematoma was descriptively more prevalent in females (6.1% vs. 1.0%, OR=0.16), Fisher's Exact Tests showed that neither difference reached statistical significance ($p=0.212$ and $p=0.118$, respectively). These non-significant results should be interpreted in the context of the low absolute frequencies of these findings and the study's limited statistical power for detecting differences in rare events – a recognised limitation of single-centre descriptive studies with moderate sample sizes. Furthermore, the multiple inferential comparisons performed across clinical indications and CT findings were not corrected for multiplicity; all analyses are exploratory, and the probability of at least one spuriously significant result increases with the number of comparisons. Findings should therefore be interpreted with caution and confirmed in larger, adequately powered studies. Nevertheless, the descriptive trend for intracerebral haematoma being more common in females remains clinically noteworthy. Ruiz-Sandoval et al.²³ reported hypertension and vascular malformations as the most frequent causes of intracerebral haemorrhage in young people, and sex-specific haemorrhagic risk differences have been linked to hormonal and haemostatic factors. A larger multicentre study with comprehensive clinical risk factor data is needed to evaluate this observation.

BMI and BSA were recorded as baseline descriptive measures. Although these variables were not analysed inferentially in the present study, their systematic documentation provides a foundation for future studies investigating associations between anthropometric and metabolic risk factors and CT findings. Taken together, the inferential findings demonstrate that the pattern of brain CT diagnoses at AKTH is not significantly sex-stratified, which has practical implications for clinical triage and protocol development at this institution.

This study has several limitations to consider. First, the study was conducted at a single tertiary institution over an eight-month period, which may

limit the generalizability of findings to other settings in Nigeria or sub-Saharan Africa. Second, the age restriction (17–65 years) excluded paediatric and geriatric patients. The upper age limit of 65 years was applied to limit confounding from age-related degenerative changes prevalent in older populations at this institution and to maintain a more homogeneous adult sample; however, this means results may not be generalisable to individuals over 65, in whom cerebrovascular and neurodegenerative pathologies are disproportionately common, who may carry distinct CT findings profiles; results therefore do not represent the full lifespan spectrum of nTBI. Third, CT findings were obtained from radiologist reports rather than from independent re-review of the images by the investigator, introducing potential inter-reporter variability. Fourth, clinical risk factor data (e.g., hypertension, diabetes, smoking status) were not collected, precluding analysis of the relationship between risk factors and CT findings.

Conclusion

Stroke was the most frequent clinical indication while proptosis, subdural haematoma, and transient ischaemic attack were among the least common. Normal brain study was the most common single CT finding, and cerebral infarct was the leading abnormal diagnosis. When clinical indications were reclassified into pathophysiological groups, cerebrovascular events collectively constituted the largest category (36.4%), more clearly representing the true vascular burden than any single indication label alone. When CT diagnoses were aggregated, all ischaemic infarcts combined (23.6%) were the leading abnormality group. There was no statistically significant sex difference in any individual or grouped clinical indication or CT finding. Descriptive trends for intracerebral haematoma in females and ischaemic infarct in males, while not statistically significant in this study, warrant investigation in larger multicentre studies.

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Conflict of interest

Nil

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